

PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH CRITERIA OF PROFESSIONAL IMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN STUDENTS OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. In this article, the manifestations of the professional image of students of vocational education are studied. Also, the factors affecting the development of the professional image are disclosed. In a number of our psychological studies, research was conducted related to the problem of forming the professional image of future specialists. The conclusions of our conducted research are based on the high role of the motivational field in the development of professional image

Key words: mage, formation, professional image, specialist, types of image, composition, tool, phenomenon, sociopolitical-psychology

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The results of the latest research in the field of modern education and pedagogical technologies demand an increase in professional requirements in the process of training specialist personnel. Nowadays, the need to develop a certain style of social behavior that ensures the success and efficiency of future professional activities for an individual is becoming an ever more urgent problem.

The scope of works devoted to the empirical determination of pedagogical conditions for teaching future specialists to create their own professional image has expanded. During the training period, a model was developed that allows the formation of the image component of the chosen profession, and the effectiveness of introducing this model into the practice of the university's educational process was experimentally tested. The criteria, indicators and levels of professional image formation of future specialists of various fields are determined, and its components are divided into personal, competence, communicative, behavioral and visual types.

In explaining the profession and its connection with the science of psychology, the well-known Russian psychologist K.M. Gurevich told his tariff. Careers are not permanent, they come and go. Due to the development and improvement of science and technology, some of them have completely changed,

although only the horse has been preserved. K.M. Gurevich shows the emergence and formation of professions as follows.

- 1) With the occurrence of division of labor;
- 2) Science - with the emergence and development of technology;
- 3) With the change of pharmacies.

Students studying at a professional educational institution experience a number of changes during their studies, including social relationships, relationships with themselves, people, their chosen profession, and society. It is during this period that the development of professional characteristics of a person is more observed, and for this reason, we have chosen this period in our research.

A total of 120 respondents were involved in the study: 65 students of Surkhandarya Abu Ali Ibn Sino Public Health Technical College and Surkhandarya Legal Technical College, 55 students of Sherabod District Pedagogical Technical College and Sherabod Abu Ali Ibn Sina Public Health Technical College.

Table 1

Indicators about the gender of the participants in the study

Terters	N	%
Girls	78	65
Boys	42	35
Total	120	100,0

In our research work, we present the following information on the sexes of the examinees who participated in the psychological diagnostic tests conducted in order to determine the socio-psychological aspects of the formation of the professional image among the students of the professional educational institution. A total of 120 respondents took part in the experimental tests, of which 78 were girls and 42 were boys.

We have presented these indicators in the form of a diagram.

Picture 2.1. Gender indicators of the participants in the study.

Table 2.2

Indicators of participants in the study by regions.

Testers	N	%
Termiz city	65	54,5
Sherabod district	55	45,5
Total	120	100,0

In order to substantiate one of the innovations of our work dedicated to the study of the formation of a professional image in the students of a professional educational institution, i.e., the expression of the orientation of young people to the profession, based on psychodiagnostic research and the research of the socio-psychological aspects of the formation of the image, We studied the data. The distribution of the respondents who participated in the study by regions was analyzed as follows. There were 65 test takers from Termiz city and 54.5 percent, while 55 test takers from Sherabod district took part and 45.5 percent. We have presented these indicators in the form of a diagram.

Picture 2.2. Indicators of the subjects participating in the study by region.

In our research work, in order to determine the psychological aspects of professional image development among students of a professional educational institution:

We carried out diagnostic experiments using the questionnaire "Determining personal motivation" proposed by V. Gerbachevsky and the methodology "Activating students' career guidance" authored by N. Pryajnikov.

We studied the problem of studying the social and psychological characteristics of the professional image among students of a professional educational institution. First, we tried to determine which scale of their motivation is dominant in order to determine the content of this feature.

First, we conducted a questionnaire "Determination of personal motivation" to obtain primary data about the psychological characteristics of the professional image of students. The main goal was to determine the importance of social and psychological characteristics of the professional image of students and the dependence of motivation on the expression of these characteristics. The results of this survey were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The results of the quantitative analysis are shown in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3.

Statistical difference based on the Mann-Whitney criterion of the questionnaire "Determination of personal motivation" (V. Gerbachevskiy) by gender. (N=120)

Scales	Average colors		U	P
	boys (n=42)	girls (n=78)		
Internal motive	157,92	163,01	-,503	,615
Motive to know	149,06	171,66	-2,227	,026**
The motive of avoiding defeat	160,94	160,07	-,085	,932
Competitive motive	152,98	167,84	-1,447	,148
Motive for switching activities	145,62	175,02	-2,858	,004**
The motive of self-respect	156,61	164,30	-,785	,433
Motive of appreciation of achievements	158,41	162,54	-,402	,688
Difficulty of assignments	144,33	176,27	-3,129	,002**
Willpower	150,40	170,35	-1,945	,050*
Levels of assessment of the results achieved	155,15	165,72	-1,095	,274
Assessment of one's capabilities	160,07	160,92	-,085	,932
The level of ability to mobilize one's own strength	157,13	163,79	-,653	,514
Level of expected results	155,17	165,70	-1,055	,292
Legitimacy of results	150,40	171,35	-1,555	,050*
Initiative	170,25	150,85	-,727	,047*

Initially, the level of motivational components that make up the personality system in students of a professional educational institution was

determined. In the questionnaire "Determining personal motivation", the components of the motivational structure are traditionally divided into four groups. The first group includes six components, which represent the core of a person's motivational structure. Taking into account the importance of the motivational structure of a person in creating a professional image, we conducted experimental diagnostic work on students using this method.

The questionnaire "Determination of personal motivation" was conducted among the selected respondents, students of the professional educational institution. According to the results of the research, girls have an advantage in the scale of the first internal motive, but the difference is not significant. We can explain this result by the presence of internal motivation in students of both genders, unlike the gender of the students, and the fact that they learn with interest the information of the lessons conducted in the specialties they are studying. ($U=-.503$; $p>.615$).

The second scale is explained by the fact that there are differences between girls and boys in the motive of knowledge, that is, the preparation for the profession through the motive of knowledge in girls is higher than that of boys. ($U=-2.227$; $p<.026$). According to the results obtained from the examinees, the motives of learning a wide range of new knowledge, facts, events and laws were more prevalent in girls than in boys. In addition, it was found that the motives of knowing - the ways of acquiring knowledge and the actions aimed at acquiring independent education methods are also high in respondent girls.

In the third scale - the motivation to avoid defeat, the same indicators were recorded in the results of representatives of both sexes, almost no difference was observed. We expressed this indicator by the fact that students do not like the feeling of defeat. ($U=-.227085$; $p>.932$). The fact that students may show low results in their majors with subsequent consequences showed the presence of fear in them. We explain that because the motive of success creates a pleasant impression on the test takers, the feeling of defeat leads to the emergence of a feeling of injustice towards themselves.

There is a difference in the results of the test takers in the fourth scale - the scale of competitive motive, but the observed difference is not significant. ($U=-1.447$; $p>.148$). This scale expresses how much importance a person attaches to high results in his work. No difference was observed in the results of the test subjects who participated in our study because they had not yet started working in their chosen professions.

Among the selected respondents, a higher rate was found in girls compared to boys in the fifth scale - motivation to change activities. ($U=-2.858$; $p<.004$). According to this motive component, it was revealed that girls have a motive to change their major. It can be explained by the fact that the tendency to stop the work that one is engaged in is more common in girls, and it means that it is allowed to rush during the choice of profession, and on the other hand, it can be explained by the fact that, on the other hand, girls are more likely to find a new profession and adapt to it more quickly.

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The second group of the questionnaire "Determining personal motivation" included the components of motivation related to the achievement of very difficult goals. These components are related to current events, and the data we received during the pilot tests allowed us to get information about the professional image of students and their thoughts at the moment.

In the seventh scale - the motive of appreciation of achievements, there was a relative difference in the results of both sexes, but the difference was not significant. ($U=-.402$; $p>.688$). Compared to girls, the respondents give a little more personal importance to the results of their activities, but the difference is not very significant. - we can justify it by the fact that their mothers give importance to them.

According to the results obtained in the difficulty of the eighth scale, the girls had a higher score, and a significant difference was observed in girls compared to boys. ($U=-3.129$; $p<.002$). It was observed that among the selected test subjects, when given tasks according to the level of complexity of the task, the girls perform the tasks responsibly, perform the difficult task diligently, and do not leave the attention of the teachers. We can explain that unlike girls, boys have such characteristics as lack of self-confidence in approaching complex tasks, fear of making mistakes, a little shyness in expressing their thoughts, and patience in expressing themselves.

According to the results of the ninth scale of willpower, girls have a higher score, and a significant difference was observed in girls compared to boys. ($U=-1.945$; $p<.050$). Through this scale, we had the opportunity to determine the manifestation of voluntary action in the respondents. Voluntary action in the process of working on a given task depends on willpower. It was determined that girls are responsible for completing the tasks assigned to them according to the professional field they are studying. It was found that the characteristic of making efforts to have a good professional image is superior in female test takers. evaluates the level of expression. It was found out that young men have ideas about having an image while performing the given tasks without exerting willpower, that is, without professional training. This can be explained by the fact that young men feel that external characteristics are more important than internal characteristics of a person in having a professional image.

It was observed that there was no significant difference in the results of representatives of both sexes from the tenth scale - the scale of evaluation levels of the achieved results. ($U=-1.095$; $p>.274$). According to the results of the scale, which allows to assess the level of the results achieved by the examinees, both boys and girls feel connected with their opportunities in the chosen activity, but they do not have a full idea of strengthening the professional image with this motive, which affects their performance. we can explain.

The results of the respondents were almost the same in the eleventh scale - the scale of self-assessment, and no significant difference was observed. ($U=-.085$; $p>.932$). It can be explained by the fact that the respondents have not yet fully started their professional activities, and they did not have an adequate approach to assessing their potential.

The third group of the questionnaire "Determination of personal motivation" includes the possibility of predictive assessment of the subject's activity. This, in turn, ensures that they understand how to create and strengthen their professional image through personal motivation.

The twelfth scale - There is a difference in the indicators of the test subjects on the level of ability to mobilize their own strength, but it is not significant. ($U=-.653$; $p>.514$). Respondents are developing knowledge and skills to mobilize actions necessary to achieve activity goals, but they are still not at the level of competence. That's why we can say that the manifestation of the level of achieving a clear goal in the activity was not recorded at a high rate in both boys and girls.

In the 13th scale - the scale of the level of expected results, a slight advantage was observed in the female test-takers compared to the boys, but no significant difference was detected. ($U=-1.055$; $p>.292$). It was noted that the difference in this scale is not significant because the expected level of performance results of our respondents has not yet been realized.

The fourth group of the questionnaire "Determination of personal motivation" reflects the causal factors of the relevant activity and combines two components.

In the fourteenth scale - the scale of legitimacy of results, a higher result was found in girls compared to boys. ($U=-1.555$; $p<.050$). From the testers, we explain that the girls have the ability to understand their potential in achieving their goals, act accordingly, and see the results of their actions in success. It can be explained by the relative lack of confidence in the young respondents that they can see the results of their efforts successfully even if they understand their possibilities in achieving their goals.

In the fifteenth scale - initiative scale, boys had a relatively higher result than girls. ($U=-.727$; $p<.047$). It was found that boys show more initiative and resourcefulness in solving tasks than girls. It was found that boys show more initiative when given individual tasks or when tasks are assigned to a group of boys. Girls show initiative and resourcefulness in solving tasks, difficulty in coming to a decision, lack of independence, restrictions such as "you are a girl, it's a boy's job" cause girls to limit their initiative. we explain.

The above-mentioned components represent the potential motivational structure that occurs during the performance of the task, and became the basis for reaching a number of conclusions during our diagnostic work.

In our research work, we carried out diagnostic experiments using the methodology "Activating the orientation of students to the profession" authored by N. Pryajnikov.[72] The purpose of the methodology is to develop students' understanding of their readiness for professional work, and we have made good use of the fact that group work of the methodology helps to determine the readiness of the student to choose a profession. Quantitative and qualitative analyzes of the results obtained from the methodology were carried out, the results of the quantitative analysis are presented in Table 2.4.

2.4 - table.

Statistical difference based on the Mann-Whitney criterion of the "Activation of vocational guidance of students" (N.Pryajnikov) method by gender. (N=120)

Scales	Average colors		U	P
	Boys (n=42)	Girls (n=78)		
Self-assessment- professional readiness	157,49	169,44	-,776	,047*

According to the results of the research conducted among the selected respondents and students, it was found that there are differences between girls and boys in the scale of Self-Assessment-Professional Readiness. The results of girls are explained by higher indicators than boys on the scale of self-assessment-professional readiness. ($U=-.776$; $p<.047$). The test girls are characterized by the ability to successfully perform various actions, the desire to improve based on the standards specified in the methodology, the desire to perform labor actions, and the presence of an attempt to activate self-knowledge. This will help the respondent girls to come to the necessary conclusions about self-evaluation in the overall assessment of their readiness for a specific profession.

Summary

It can be explained by the fact that although the chosen young people are interested in the profession, they are slow in performing work activities, and tend to be supported in activating self-knowledge, which led to an adequate self-evaluation. Therefore, it may be difficult for young men to make a general assessment of their readiness for a specific profession, to come to conclusions about self-evaluation.

Of course, conclusions about high or low self-esteem have a conditional character, because several teenagers are surprised by their ability to successfully perform various actions. We conclude that checking the readiness of students for professions, the psychologist paying attention to these professions, and discussing the types of activities that teenagers are interested in together with the pedagogue will ensure the achievement of an effective result. Because it activates a person's thoughts about self-knowledge and personal capabilities, as well as ensures that he can successfully determine his own destiny.

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